

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D4.1

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

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ABSTRACT

The Euratom HARPERS project aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of a more aligned practices and approaches for prioritised topics related to decommissioning and initial phases of radioactive waste handling.

The HARPERS project has a two-phase approach, the first phase involves engaging with Stakeholders to assess needs and pros/cons for harmonisation and to identify priority areas for deeper analysis, the second phase will pursue deeper engagement with Stakeholders to further assess the highest ranked priority areas in the technical Work Packages.

The goal of HARPERS Work Package 4 is to address the most important conditions and opportunities for promoting Circular Economy approaches when managing materials and waste arising from nuclear decommissioning across Europe. As part of Phase 1, a list of topics has been proposed for deep analysis in Phase 2. Two online workshops allowed to collect feedback from interested stakeholders to support the topic prioritisation process. A specific methodology was devised and used to select top 3 prioritised topics to be studied in Phase 2 of the HARPERS project.

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CONTENTS

VERSION HISTORY - 6 -

1 OBJECTIVE..... - 7 -

2 IDENTIFICATION OF TOPICS - 7 -

3 INVOLVEMENT OF STAKEHOLDER COMMUNITY - 12 -

 3.1 WORKSHOP DATES AND AGENDA..... - 13 -

 3.2 WORKSHOP SESSIONS AND RESULTS..... - 14 -

4 PRIORITISATION METHODOLOGY AND PROCESS..... - 17 -

 4.1 DEFINITION OF THE WEIGHTING FACTORS OF CATEGORIES AND DRIVERS..... - 18 -

 4.2 DEFINITION OF THE MAIN CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH THE DIFFERENT TOPICS AND THEIR WEIGHTING FACTORS..... - 19 -

 4.3 ASSIGNMENT OF THE CHALLENGES TO THE TOPICS - 21 -

 4.4 ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF THE TOPICS ON THE DRIVERS - 30 -

 4.5 FINAL SELECTION OF THE PRIORITY TOPICS - 35 -

5 TOP PRIORITIZED TOPICS..... - 38 -

FIGURE

Figure 1: HARPERS project structure - 7 -

Figure 2: “Word cloud” from 1st (left) and 2nd (right) workshops - 14 -

Figure 3: Drivers (1st workshop left – 2nd workshop right) - 15 -

Figure 4: Categories (1st workshop left – 2nd workshop right) - 16 -

Figure 5: Barriers/challenges for reuse and recycling (1st workshop left – 2nd workshop right)..... - 16 -

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Figure 6: Barriers/challenges for clearance (1st workshop left – 2nd workshop right). - 17 -	
Figure 7: Importance Vs Urgency matrix - 36 -	
Figure 8: Impact vs Effort matrix..... - 37 -	

TABLE

Table 1: List of Topics - 10 -	
Table 2: List of selection criteria for prioritisation process. - 12 -	
Table 3: Quantification of the Weighting Factors for the Categories - 18 -	
Table 4: Quantification of the Weighting Factors for the Drivers - 19 -	
Table 5: Results on the Challenges/barriers derived from the 2 Workshops - 20 -	
Table 6: Weighting Factors for the Challenges..... - 20 -	
Table 7: Challenges and needs assigned to the revised topic list (colour highlighted – challenges selected by the WP4 partners, numbers – results of the exercise held during the Frascati Consortium Meeting) - 25 -	
Table 8: Matrix for the analysis of the impacts on the drivers and topics score - 34 -	
Table 9: Topics considered for the final selection..... - 35 -	
Table 10: Top Prioritised Topics..... - 38 -	

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

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Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

1 Objective

The aim of the HARPERS project is to better align practices and approaches in decommissioning and initial phase of radioactive waste management between Member States (MS).

Work Package (WP) 4 aims to identify the most important conditions and opportunities that can help to promote Circular Economy when managing materials and waste coming from nuclear decommissioning across Europe.

Task 4.1 (Phase 1a) is focused on the prioritisation of needs and opportunities for Circular Economy considerations. As a result of this task, 3 top priority topics were defined. These topics will be further analysed in the scope of Task 4.2 (Phase 2).

Figure 1: HARPERS project structure

Deliverable D4.1 describes the identification of topics, the prioritisation methodology and its outcomes.

2 Identification of topics

In order to identify priority areas related to the objectives of the WP4 a first list of challenges and needs were identified during the proposal phase and an extensive “gap analysis” was performed by consulting relevant documentation such as Strategic

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Research Agenda's (SRA), State of the Art reports (SOTA), position papers, surveys, etc.

The gap analysis outcomes together with the challenges and needs identified in the proposal phase were discussed and analysed with the WP4 team members. They were further combined/integrated into a final list of topics that were grouped into categories. Afterwards, the topic list was reviewed prior to the discussion with the Stakeholder community. The final list of topics included in the different categories is reported in the following Table 1.

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY
INVENTORY	1	Common waste and radioactive materials recyclable or reusable	Surveying to find common issues for harmonised approach
	2	Classification and management of hazardous waste - link with European Green Deal (Circular Economy Action Plan) and the Waste Regulation	Maintain clean recycling streams and increase the confidence in using secondary raw materials
	3	Harmonised system to classify waste to promote circularity Inventory management as a prerequisite for circular economy	Optimising the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact
RECYCLING AND REUSE	4	Availability of technology and facilities to process waste / Benchmarking of technology for recycling and reuse	Create a system for by-products and raw materials exchange between nuclear facilities' waste generators and potential end-users (industrial symbiosis approach).
	5	Available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field	Gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning
	6	R&D for new technologies for recovery, recycling and reusing of materials	Increase efficiency / reduce cost
	7	Reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site)	Minimise waste and recover and reuse valuable materials
	8	Create markets for recycled materials / Enable routes for cleared wastes (e.g., metals)	Further promote recycling of materials and reduce costs
	9	Compliance of the recycling option with the applicable regulation (including clearance and specific criteria for recycling)	Improve environmental sustainability (preserve natural resources).

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

	10	Identification of criteria for material reusing (e.g., quality, durability, ...) - focused on material physico-chemical characteristics	Promote material reusing and reduce generation of waste
	11	Recycled materials traceability	Harmonised systems to track and manage information on recycled materials
	12	Quality assessment of recycled materials (in comparison with a new one)	Promote use and create market for recycled materials
	13	Safety and ALARA issues for recycling	
	14	Costs and time needed for implementation of recycling solutions	
	15	Public expectation / constraint, transparency and engagement around reusing and recycling	Raising public awareness on circular economy issues + societal engagement to enable recycling
TECHNOLOGIES FOR MATERIAL AND WASTE TREATMENT	16	Benchmarking of technologies and facilities for radioactive material and waste treatment	Create a widespread and structured system of technologies/facilities to be more effective
	17	Mobile system	Reduce environmental impact and enable reuse and recycling
	18	Optimisation of treatment technologies (e.g.decontamination)	Minimise waste and facilitate reuse and recycling
CLEARANCE	19	Free release of waste and materials arising from decommissioning (framework for clearance and regulatory discrepancies - Harmonised regulations to enable recycling)	Minimise waste to be disposed of. Optimising the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact
	20	Unconditional clearance: use of general limits	Promote reuse (for free release)
		Conditional clearance: no international guidance but only national and site-specific	Promote recycling in nuclear and non-nuclear field for conditional clearance
21	Clearance of very lightly contaminated liquids		
CHARACTERISATION	22	Facilities for free release	Enhance flexibility on characterisation approaches to be used for material clearance
	23	Conservative clearance standards can still be a challenge	
	24	Regulatory requirements could consider different approaches: e.g., statistical approaches	
MULTI CRITERIA ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES	25	Digital tools and advanced technologies to support decision making processes and circular economy principles	Facilitate quick decision making and optimise decommissioning, waste management and radiation protection.

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

	26	Socio-economical assessments of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular)	Cost-benefit analysis to evaluate the option of reuse and recycle and facilitate decision making
	27	Multicriteria decision making for final end-state	
TRANSVERSAL	28	Sharing good practices	Crosscutting to all the previous topics
	29	Regulatory/Public engagement	
	30	Knowledge Management and Training	
	31	Various Stakeholder integration	

Table 1: List of Topics

A common set of selection criteria which correspond to drivers for implementation in decommissioning and waste management were defined (see Table 2). These relate to societal, actor-specific, scientific and financial impacts. These drivers are being used in the development of the SRA for the PREDIS (“PREDISposal management of radioactive waste”) project and were based on work undertaken in the SHARE project.

Driver	Description
	Societal: Societal impacts address higher level area economics, perspectives of people, environmental protection and the overall trust and well-being of the society. These can be viewed at a local, municipality, regional, country or EU level.
Economic renewal and growth	Leads to a sustainable increase in the number of work force/jobs and services needed, allowing existing companies to expand their offering or for new companies to enter the market. Provides economic benefits to a region, which can impact the quality and availability of societal public services in the area. Also linked to financial impacts.
Protection of citizens and environment	Leads to improved protection of citizens and the environment by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting the reduction of radioactive waste volumes, including between classes of waste (e.g. reduction in HLW to lower levels of waste)

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Driver	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving waste classification • Supporting the conservation of the environment • Reducing hazards • Applying the waste hierarchy to prevent, minimise, re-use and recycle wastes • Reducing secondary waste production • Enables safer treatment, packing and storage of wastes, reducing the risk of human exposure (worker and public) and environmental accidents
Public trust and confidence	Engenders public trust and confidence through good planning, implementation and communication of programmes; good communication and transparency of decision making by regulators and governments; and timely and efficient policy formulation and implementation.
Actor-specific: Actor-specific impacts reflect individual company or industry advances relating to processes, products and services, efficiency, competences	
Processes, products and services	Supports the development of new / improved and innovative processes, products and services to address pre-disposal management, which in turn leads to the creation and expansion of companies. Provides solutions that create a competitive advantage, such as cost reduction or resource efficiency. Provides
Capacity to improve performance	Provides improved performance by increasing the efficiency of tasks (e.g. by reducing the required labour and minimising the generation of secondary waste) and by reducing lead times for pre-disposal management by reducing the time needed for each task. Supports the reduction in regulatory review times by integrating this
Contribution to competences and skills development	Supports the development and maintenance of a skilled and competent workforce for the duration of pre-disposal management programmes. Provides training, education and certification of the workforce, and services/tools for knowledge management, helping

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Driver	Description
Improvement of national/international networks	Provides benefits to research and business communities through participation in research networks and business networks. Supports mobility between companies and combining expertise
Scientific: Scientific impacts relate to technology development and innovation to drive improvements.	
Quality in science and technology development	Builds competences and skills in state-of-the-art technologies, practices and developments, through research collaboration and publication of work to assess research quality. Advances technology through Technology Readiness Levels (TRL).
Innovation capacity	Develops innovation capacity to both introduce new products, services and processes to the market, and to develop in-house solutions.
Financial: Financial impacts relate to business solutions (linked to company growth and performance) and funding schemes.	
Revenue and turnover	Increases revenue and turnover of a company, leading to increased company growth and improved performance through demonstrating high quality services, tools and success in delivery. Dependent on market potential and funding schemes, as well as ability to reduce liabilities.
Sufficient investment	Promotes adequate funding for predisposal management, and investment in the required supporting infrastructure and facilities.

Table 2: List of selection criteria for prioritisation process.

3 Involvement of Stakeholder Community

For the stakeholder engagement, two online workshops were organised to define priority needs and opportunities. The list of identified topics was discussed during the

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

two workshops in order to collect the feedback of external stakeholders and project partners (as internal one) for the prioritisation.

The workshops included technical presentations from HARPERS partners and participants engagement through online polls with Slido tool and Q&A/open discussion session.

3.1 Workshop Dates and Agenda

Two sessions of the workshops were organized on 16th January and 22nd February 2023. The agenda of both sessions is presented below:

10.00-10.05	Workshop Opening <i>WP4 Leader (F. Pancotti - SOGIN)</i>
10.05-10.15	General introduction HARPERS Project <i>Project Coordinator (R. Szóke - IFE)</i>
10.15-10.30	Participants Self Introduction <i>Moderator: F. Pancotti (SOGIN)</i>
10.30-10.50	Part 1 _ Circular Economy Introduction + Slido Polls <i>F. Pancotti (SOGIN)</i>
10.50-11.10	Q&A - Open Discussion <i>Moderator: F. Pancotti (SOGIN)</i> <i>Support: R. Sciacqua (SOGIN) – A. Bruno (AMPHOS 21) – L. Vaillant (CEPN)</i>
11.10-11.15	Break
11.15-11.35	Part 2 _ Circular Economy Topic Description + Slido Polls <i>F. Pancotti (SOGIN)</i>
11.35-11.55	Q&A - Open Discussion <i>Moderator: F. Pancotti (SOGIN)</i> <i>Support: R. Sciacqua (SOGIN) – A. Bruno (AMPHOS 21) – L. Vaillant (CEPN)</i>
11.55-12.00	Closure of the Workshop <i>F. Pancotti (SOGIN)</i>

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Regarding the drivers for implementing circular economy in radioactive waste management (Figure 3), participants clearly indicated “Protection of citizens and environment”, “Economic renewal and growth” and “Public trust and confidence” as the top 3 drivers.

Figure 3: Drivers (1st workshop left – 2nd workshop right)

The second part of the workshops were devoted to a description of the topics included in the different categories.

Results of the pools (Figure 4) showed that participants indicated “Recycling and Reuse” and “Clearance” as the most important topics for future work within HARPERS project. No strong expectations were highlighted with regards to “Inventory” or “Characterisation”.

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Figure 4: Categories (1st workshop left – 2nd workshop right)

When it comes to “Barriers/Challenges” for Reuse and Recycling (Figure 5) and for Clearance (Figure 6), participants clearly outline regulatory discrepancies and regulatory constraints as the main challenge for clearance and material recycling. Societal aspects were indicated as a dominant theme and sharing of current/good practices could help in building trust in the recycling of materials with very low level or even no contamination.

Figure 5: Barriers/challenges for reuse and recycling (1st workshop left – 2nd workshop right)

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Figure 6: Barriers/challenges for clearance (1st workshop left – 2nd workshop right)

From the Stakeholder involvement point of view, both the workshops had a good engagement with the Slido polls, during the open discussion it was possible to express own opinion.

By all the results of the webinars polls, the most important themes for future work within HARPERS are recycling and reuse, clearance and multi criteria analysis of strategy.

During the discussions set in the webinars, societal aspect was a dominant point. A change of mind is needed, and the workforce should be educated to become more familiar with circular economy principles and practices.

A lot of attention was also given to stakeholder trust and to public perception. Knowledge sharing and the importance of stakeholder engagement were related to the driver: *build trust and competence*.

4 Prioritisation methodology and process

A semi-quantitative approach was developed for the Prioritisation of Topics. This approach was based on the identification of Weighting Factors of different Categories, Drivers and to the Challenges, taken from the results of the two Workshops and consolidated within WP4, assigned to the different topics. Next, the impact of the topics

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

on the top drivers was evaluated. The final selection of the 3 topics to move to Phase 2 was done collectively by WP4 partners with a qualitative evaluation of the top priority topics in terms of “Importance, Urgency and Achievability”.

On 9th May 2023 the Topic Prioritisation Meeting took place, finalizing the list of 3 Prioritised Topics. A detailed description of the Semi-qualitative methodology and the Prioritisation process is given in the next subchapters.

4.1 Definition of the weighting factors of Categories and Drivers

For each Category and Driver a relative weight was assigned, based on the output of the two Workshops (Slido polls – see Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6) and WP4 discussion.

The quantification of the Weighting Factors was based on the outcomens of the two Workshops (mean value). The relative percentages of importance of the different Categories/Drivers were normalised to the highest one to obtain the Weighting Factors in the range 0 -1 (see Table 3 and Table 4).

CATEGORIES	1st WS		2nd WS		mean	WF
	Q3 (%)	Q6 (%)	Q3 (%)	Q6 (%)	%	
INVENTORY	12	16	7	4	10	0,2
RECYCLING AND REUSE	60	52	59	64	59	1,0
TECHNOLOGIES FOR MATERIAL AND WASTE TREATMENT	16	8	19	16	15	0,3
CLEARANCE	44	44	41	52	45	0,8
CHARACTERISATION	8	12	15	12	12	0,2
MULTI CRITERIA ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES	32	28	22	36	30	0,5
TRANSVERSAL	20	16	30	16	21	0,3

Table 3: Quantification of the Weighting Factors for the Categories

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

DRIVERS	1st WS	2nd WS	mean	WF
	Q2 (%)	Q2 (%)	%	
Economic renewal and growth	43	46	45	0,6
Protection of citizens and environment	74	65	70	1,0
Public trust and confidence	43	58	51	0,7
Processes, products and services	13	12	13	0,2
Capacity to improve performance	13	12	13	0,2
Contribution to competences and skills development	4	19	12	0,2
Improvement of national/international networks	35	19	27	0,4
Quality in science and technology development	13	12	13	0,2
Innovation capacity	22	35	29	0,4
Revenue and turnover	9	8	9	0,1
Sufficient investment	13	4	9	0,1

Table 4: Quantification of the Weighting Factors for the Drivers

4.2 Definition of the main Challenges associated with the different topics and their Weighting Factors

Different Challenges needed to be considered/analysed for each topic. These Challenges were defined, considering what was discussed during the two Workshops (Slido polls - see Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6), and consolidated within WP4.

The list of challenges includes:

1. **Technological and operational** challenges (e.g. availability of technologies/facilities for waste processing/recycling and characterisation) - NEED to improve technology/innovate and improve operational excellence;
2. **Regulatory** challenges linked with different national regulations (legal framework/licensing) – NEED to improve/develop regulations/policies and/or for harmonisation of approaches/development of guidance.

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

3. **Different approaches** implemented in different Countries (e.g. for materials traceability/quality assurance, guidance for clearance) – NEED for sharing experiences and best practice;
4. **Economical** challenges (cost/benefit) – NEED for cost - effective solutions;
5. **Societal** (e.g. public constraints, stakeholder issues, public perception on cleared materials) – NEED to engage with the public.

For each challenge a Weighting Factor was assigned. The first quantification of the Weighting Factor, based on the output of the two Workshops (Figure 5 and Figure 6), was proposed by the WP4 leader (see Table 6) based on the partial results derived from the analysis of the outcomes of the two Workshops (see Table 5) and further consolidated within WP4.

RECYCLING AND REUSE	1st WS	2nd WS	mean	WF
	Q4	Q4		
Technological and operational (availability of technologies/facilities)	2,35	2,31	2,33	0,6
Regulatory (legal framework/licensing)	3,62	4,23	3,925	1,0
Safety and ALARA issues (doses to workers during waste processing)	0,96	0,46	0,71	0,2
Economical (cost/benefit)	2,27	1,69	1,98	0,5
Societal (public constraints, stakeholder issues)	2,35	2,27	2,31	0,6
CLEARANCE	1st WS	2nd WS	mean	WF
	Q5	Q5		
Regulatory (legal framework)	3,21	4,48	3,845	1,0
Cleared materials traceability	1,21	0,6	0,905	0,2
Public perception on cleared materials	2,71	2,08	2,395	0,6
Availability of guidance for clearance	1,96	1,88	1,92	0,5
Technologies and approaches for characterisation	1,96	1,72	1,84	0,5

Table 5: Results on the Challenges/barriers derived from the 2 Workshops

CHALLENGES	WF
Technological and operational	0,5
Different National Regulations	1,0
Different approaches	0,5
Economical	0,5
Societal	0,6

Table 6: Weighting Factors for the Challenges

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

4.3 Assignment of the challenges to the topics

After a review of the topics (some of them have been combined to reduce the total number see Table 7), the main challenges (from 1 to 3) have been assigned to each topic, based on the WP4 Partners experience and knowledge.

This activity started with the analysis of the outcomes of an exercise conducted during the Consortium meeting held in Frascati (20th – 21st April 2023) where the HARPERS partners were asked to assign 1 or 2 challenges to each topic and write the specific needs of the topics.

In the following Table 7 are summarised the challenges assigned to each topic (presented by coloured boxes) as well as the results from the exercise performed during Frascati Consortium meeting (represented by the number of votes).

Finally, the Weighting Factor of each topic was calculated by multiplying Weighting Factor of topic category and the maximum Weighting Factor of the main topic challenges (see Table 8).

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY		TOPIC	CHALLENGE					NEED
			TECHNOLOGICAL AND OPERATIONAL	DIFFERENT APPROACHES	ECONOMICAL	DIFFERENT NATIONAL REGULATIONS	SOCIETAL	
INVENTORY	1	Identification of common waste and radioactive materials recyclable or reusable with the aim of analysing common issues for harmonised approach	3	4	1	1	0	Harmonisation of approaches
	2	Classification and management of hazardous waste - link with European Green Deal (Circular Economy Action Plan) and the Waste Regulation to Maintain clean recycling streams and increase the confidence in using secondary raw materials	0	0	3	5	4	Harmonisation driven by safety issues
	3	Harmonised system to classify waste to promote circularity and standardised approached for inventory management to optimise the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling. It will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact	0	0	0	8	4	Harmonisation of approaches, Societal pressure - results in different regulations
RECYCLING AND REUSE	4	Benchmarking of technology and facilities to process waste and technology for recycling and reuse to create a system for by-products and raw materials exchange between nuclear facilities' waste generators and potential end-users (industrial symbiosis approach).	3	1	1	1	0	N/A
	5	Benchmarking of available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field to gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning	6	0	2	1	1	Sharing best practices

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY		TOPIC	CHALLENGE					NEED
			TECHNOLOGICAL AND OPERATIONAL	DIFFERENT APPROACHES	ECONOMICAL	DIFFERENT NATIONAL REGULATIONS	SOCIETAL	
RECYCLING AND REUSE	6	Identification of R&D needs for new technologies for recovery, recycling and reusing of materials with the aim of increasing efficiency and reduce cost	0	0	7	2	1	Who should pay?
	7	Sharing best practices for reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site) to Minimise waste and recover and reuse valuable materials.	0	2	4	2	0	“Recycling & reuse”. It’s all about management being afraid so regulators & public see “fear”
	8	Promote use and Create markets for recycled materials and Enable routes for cleared wastes (e.g. metals): 1) Identification of criteria for material reusing (e.g. quality, durability, ...) - focused on material physico-chemical characteristics; 2) Harmonised systems to track and manage information on recycled materials 3) Quality assessment of recycled materials (in comparison with a new one) 4) Safety and ALARA issues for recycling	0	0	6	0	0	There is a lack of clear targets/goals of recycling in decommissioning
								Knowledge exchange, lesson learning and joint discussion and negotiation for regulatory development
	9	Compliance of the recycling option with the applicable regulation (including clearance and specific criteria for recycling) to improve environmental sustainability (preserve natural resources).	1	0	1	3	6	N/A
	10	Costs and time needed for implementation of recycling solutions to promote use and create market for recycled materials	2	0	6	1	2	Need for cost/benefit analysis
11	Public expectation / constraint, transparency and engagement around reusing and recycling	0	0	1	0	14	Transparency	
							Public Engagement	
							Communication	

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY		TOPIC	CHALLENGE					NEED
			TECHNOLOGICAL AND OPERATIONAL	DIFFERENT APPROACHES	ECONOMICAL	DIFFERENT NATIONAL REGULATIONS	SOCIETAL	
TECHNOLOGIES FOR MATERIAL AND WASTE TREATMENT	12	Benchmarking of technologies and facilities for radioactive material and waste treatment to create a widespread and structured system of technologies/facilities to be more effective	2	0	10	5	0	N/A
	13	Mobile system to reduce environmental impact and enable reuse and recycling	5	0	7	5	0	Link with ROUTES Task 3 asked by many SIMS countries
	14	Optimisation of treatment technologies (e.g. decontamination) to minimise waste and facilitate reuse and recycling	5	1	8	0	1	N/A
CLEARANCE	15	Identification of regulatory discrepancies for Free release, unconditional and conditional clearance of waste and materials arising from decommissioning (including very lightly contaminated liquids) in the different member states. To promote harmonised criteria and regulations to enable re-use and recycling, preserve natural resources and minimising the waste to be disposed of	2	6	0	9	5	Development of policies
								Development of guidance
								Transparency
CHARACTERISATION	16	Benchmarking of facilities for free release	1	4	2	5	1	Why is this benchmarking necessary?
	17	Enhance flexibility on characterisation approaches to be used for material clearance considering challenges associated with conservative clearance standards and different approaches: e.g statistical approaches	4	4	0	3	0	N/A

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY		TOPIC	CHALLENGE					NEED
			TECHNOLOGICAL AND OPERATIONAL	DIFFERENT APPROACHES	ECONOMICAL	DIFFERENT NATIONAL REGULATIONS	SOCIETAL	
MULTI CRITERIA ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES	18	Digital tools and advanced technologies to facilitate quick decision making and support circular economy principles	1	1	7	0	0	Engage stakeholders into participating in multicriteria analysis to include their view in decision-making, and foster a holistic assessment
								Multiactors also
								“Multicriteria analysis”. This is just to satisfy “political” reporting by the companies
	19	Socio-economical assessments of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular) - including final end-state - to evaluate the option of reuse and recycle and assess the economical, environmental/societal benefits and facilitate decision making	0	1	3	0	7	Will it really change anything?
Development of a safety + business case to analyse the benefits/disadvantages of standardization natural approach								
TRANSVERSAL	20	Knowledge Management and Training	0	3	0	3	3	Public Engagement

Table 7: Challenges and needs assigned to the revised topic list (colour highlighted – challenges selected, numbers – results of the exercise held during the Frascati Consortium Meeting)

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY	WF CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	Description of the topic	Type of challenge					TOTAL WF
				Technological and operational	Different National Regulations	Different approaches	Economical	Societal	
				0,5	1,0	0,5	0,5	0,6	
INVENTORY	0,2	1	Identification of common waste and radioactive materials recyclable or reusable with the aim of analysing common issues for harmonised approach	0,5	1,0	0,5			0,2
		2	Classification and management of hazardous waste - link with European Green Deal (Circular Economy Action Plan) and the Waste Regulation to Maintain clean recycling streams and increase the confidence in using secondary raw materials		1,0		0,5	0,6	0,2
		3	Harmonised system to classify waste to promote circularity and standardised approached for inventory management to optimise the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling. It will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact		1,0				0,2
RECYCLING AND REUSE	1,0	4	Benchmarking of technology and facilities to process waste and technology for recycling and reuse to create a system for by-products and raw materials exchange between nuclear facilities' waste generators and potential end-users (industrial symbiosis approach).	0,5					0,5
		5	Benchmarking of available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field to gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning	0,5		0,5	0,5		0,5

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY	WF CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	Description of the topic	Type of challenge					TOTAL WF
				Technological and operational	Different National Regulations	Different approaches	Economical	Societal	
				0,5	1,0	0,5	0,5	0,6	
RECYCLING AND REUSE		6	Identification of R&D needs for new technologies for recovery, recycling and reusing of materials with the aim of increasing efficiency and reduce cost	0,5			0,5		0,5
		7	sharing best practices for Reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site) to Minimise waste and recover and reuse valuable materials			0,5	0,5		0,5
		8	Promote use and Create markets for recycled materials and Enable routes for cleared wastes (e.g. metals): 1) Identification of criteria for material reusing (e.g. quality, durability, ...) - focused on material physico-chemical characteristics; 2) Harmonised systems to track and manage information on recycled materials 3) Quality assessment of recycled materials (in comparison with a new one) 4) Safety and ALARA issues for recycling			0,5	0,5		0,5
		9	Compliance of the recycling option with the applicable regulation (including clearance and specific criteria for recycling) to improve environmental sustainability (preserve natural resources).		1,0			0,6	1,0
		10	Costs and time needed for implementation of recycling solutions to promote use and create market for recycled materials	0,5			0,5		0,5

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY	WF CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	Description of the topic	Type of challenge					TOTAL WF
				Technological and operational	Different National Regulations	Different approaches	Economical	Societal	
				0,5	1,0	0,5	0,5	0,6	
		11	Public expectation / constraint, transparency and engagement around reusing and recycling					0,6	0,6
TECHNOLOGIES FOR MATERIAL AND WASTE TREATMENT	0,3	12	Benchmarking of technologies and facilities for radioactive material and waste treatment to create a widespread and structured system of technologies/facilities to be more effective		1,0				0,3
		13	Mobile system to reduce environmental impact and enable reuse and recycling	0,5	1,0		0,5		0,3
		14	Optimisation of treatment technologies (e.g. decontamination) to minimise waste and facilitate reuse and recycling	0,5			0,5		0,1
CLEARANCE	0,8	15	identification of regulatory discrepancies for Free release, unconditional and conditional clearance of waste and materials arising from decommissioning (including very lightly contaminated liquids) in the different member states. To promote the harmonised criteria and regulations to enable re-use and recycling, preserve natural resources and minimising the waste to be disposed of		1,0	0,5		0,6	0,8
CHARACTERISATION	0,2	16	benchmarking of facilities for free release		1,0	0,5			0,2
		17	Enhance flexibility on characterisation approaches to be used for material clearance considering challenges associated with conservative clearance standards and different approaches: e.g statistical approaches	0,5	1,0	0,5			0,2

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY	WF CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	Description of the topic	Type of challenge					TOTAL WF
				Technological and operational	Different National Regulations	Different approaches	Economical	Societal	
				0,5	1,0	0,5	0,5	0,6	
MULTI CRITERIA ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES	0,5	18	Digital tools and advanced technologies to facilitate quick decision making and support circular economy principles				0,5		0,3
		19	Socio-economical assessments of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular) - including final end-state - to to evaluate the option of reuse and recycle and assess the economical, environmental/societal benefits and facilitate decision making				0,5	0,6	0,3
TRANSVERSAL	0,3	20	Knowledge Management and Training			0,5			0,2

Table 8: Topics Weighting Factors

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

4.4 Analysis of the impact of the topics on the drivers

The topics were then analysed by the WP4 partners using a matrix and considering the impact (High – Medium - Low) they may have on a specific Driver. A specific value was assigned to the impact evaluation of a topic on each driver as in the following:

- **1** was assigned when the topic had **High** impact on the relative driver
- **0,5** was assigned when the topic had **Medium** impact on the relative driver
- **0,1** was assigned when the topic had **Low** impact on the relative driver

The score of each topic was then calculated as the sum of the impacts multiplied by the weight of the relative Drivers. The analysis was limited to the top 5 drivers. Topics with the final score equal or higher than 0.8 were further analysed in the next stage of prioritisation (see Table 9).

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY	n.	Description of the topic	WF	DRIVERS					Score
				Protection of citizens and environment	Public trust and confidence	Economic renewal and growth	Innovation capacity	Improvement of national/international networks	
				1,0	0,7	0,6	0,4	0,4	
INVENTORY	1	Identification of common waste and radioactive materials recyclable or reusable with the aim of analysing common issues for harmonised approach	0,2	1,0	0,5	1,0	0,1	1,0	0,4
	2	Classification and management of hazardous waste - link with European Green Deal (Circular Economy Action Plan) and the Waste Regulation to Maintain clean recycling streams and increase the confidence in using secondary raw materials	0,2	1,0	1,0	1,0	0,1	0,5	0,4
	3	Harmonised system to classify waste to promote circularity and standardised approached for inventory management to optimise the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling. It will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact	0,2	1,0	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,1	0,3
RECYCLING AND REUSE	4	Benchmarking of technology and facilities to process waste and technology for recycling and reuse to create a system for by-products and raw materials exchange between nuclear facilities' waste generators and potential end-users (industrial symbiosis approach).	0,5	0,5	0,5	1,0	0,5	1,0	1,1
	5	Benchmarking of available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field to gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning	0,5	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,7

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY	n.	Description of the topic	WF	DRIVERS					Score
				Protection of citizens and environment	Public trust and confidence	Economic renewal and growth	Innovation capacity	Improvement of national/international networks	
				1,0	0,7	0,6	0,4	0,4	
RECYCLING AND REUSE	6	Identification of R&D needs for new technologies for recovery, recycling and reusing of materials with the aim of increasing efficiency and reduce cost	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,5	1,0	0,1	0,7
	7	sharing best practices for Reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site) to Minimise waste and recover and reuse valuable materials	0,5	1,0	0,1	0,5	0,1	1,0	0,9
	8	Promote use and Create markets for recycled materials and Enable routes for cleared wastes (e.g. metals): 1) Identification of criteria for material reusing (e.g. quality, durability, ...) - focused on material physico-chemical characteristics; 2) Harmonised systems to track and manage information on recycled materials 3) Quality assessment of recycled materials (in comparison with a new one) 4) Safety and ALARA issues for recycling	0,5	0,5	1,0	1,0	0,5	0,5	1,1
	9	Compliance of the recycling option with the applicable regulation (including clearance and specific criteria for recycling) to improve environmental sustainability (preserve natural resources).	1,0	1,0	1,0	0,5	0,1	0,5	2,3
	10	Costs and time needed for implementation of recycling solutions to promote use and create market for recycled materials	0,5	0,5	0,5	1,0	0,1	0,5	0,9
	11	Public expectation / constraint, transparency and engagement around reusing and recycling	0,6	0,5	1,0	0,5	0,1	1,0	1,2

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY	n.	Description of the topic	WF	DRIVERS					Score
				Protection of citizens and environment	Public trust and confidence	Economic renewal and growth	Innovation capacity	Improvement of national/international networks	
				1,0	0,7	0,6	0,4	0,4	
TECHNOLOGIES FOR MATERIAL AND WASTE TREATMENT	12	Benchmarking of technologies and facilities for radioactive material and waste treatment to create a widespread and structured system of technologies/facilities to be more effective	0,3	0,5	0,5	1,0	0,5	1,0	0,5
	13	Mobile system to reduce environmental impact and enable reuse and recycling	0,3	1,0	0,1	0,5	0,5	1,0	0,5
	14	Optimisation of treatment technologies (e.g. decontamination) to minimise waste and facilitate reuse and recycling	0,1	1,0	0,5	1,0	1,0	0,5	0,4
CLEARANCE	15	identification of regulatory discrepancies for Free release, unconditional and conditional clearance of waste and materials arising from decommissioning (including very lightly contaminated liquids) in the different member states. To promote the harmonised criteria and regulations to enable re-use and recycling, preserve natural resources and minimising the waste to be disposed of	0,8	1,0	1,0	1,0	0,1	1,0	2,2
CHARACTERISATION	16	benchmarking of facilities for free release	0,2	0,5	0,5	1,0	0,5	1,0	0,4
	17	Enhance flexibility on characterisation approaches to be used for material clearance considering challenges associated with conservative clearance standards and different approaches: e.g statistical approaches	0,2	0,5	0,1	1,0	0,5	0,5	0,3
MULTI CRITERIA ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES	18	Digital tools and advanced technologies to facilitate quick decision making and support circular economy principles	0,3	1,0	0,5	1,0	1,0	0,5	0,7

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

CATEGORY	n.	Description of the topic	WF	DRIVERS					Score
				Protection of citizens and environment	Public trust and confidence	Economic renewal and growth	Innovation capacity	Improvement of national/international networks	
				1,0	0,7	0,6	0,4	0,4	
	19	Socio-economical assessments of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular) - including final end-state - to to evaluate the option of reuse and recycle and assess the economical, environmental/societal benefits and facilitate decision making	0,3	1,0	1,0	1,0	0,5	0,1	0,8
TRANSVERSAL	20	Knowledge Management and Training	0,2	0,5	1,0	0,1	0,1	1,0	0,3

Table 9: Matrix for the analysis of the impacts on the drivers and topics score

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

4.5 Final selection of the priority topics

The selected topics analysed during the final selection are presented in Table 10.

n.	Description of the topic
4	Benchmarking of technology and facilities to process waste and technology for recycling and reuse to create a system for by-products and raw materials exchange between nuclear facilities' waste generators and potential end-users (industrial symbiosis approach).
5	Benchmarking of available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field to gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning
7	sharing best practices for Reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site) to Minimise waste and recover and reuse valuable materials
8	Promote use and Create markets for recycled materials and Enable routes for cleared wastes (e.g. metals): 1) Identification of criteria for material reusing (e.g. quality, durability, ...) - focused on material physico-chemical characteristics; 2) Harmonised systems to track and manage information on recycled materials 3) Quality assessment of recycled materials (in comparison with a new one) 4) Safety and ALARA issues for recycling
9	Compliance of the recycling option with the applicable regulation (including clearance and specific criteria for recycling) to improve environmental sustainability (preserve natural resources).
10	Costs and time needed for implementation of recycling solutions to promote use and create market for recycled materials
11	Public expectation / constraint, transparency and engagement around reusing and recycling
15	identification of regulatory discrepancies for Free release, unconditional and conditional clearance of waste and materials arising from decommissioning (including very lightly contaminated liquids) in the different member states. To promote the harmonised criteria and regulations to enable re-use and recycling, preserve natural resources and minimising the waste to be disposed of
19	Socio-economical assessments of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular) - including final end-state - to evaluate the option of reuse and recycle and assess the economical, environmental/societal benefits and facilitate decision making

Table 10: Topics considered for the final selection

The final selection of the top 3 priority topics that will be further analysed in Phase 2 of the HARPERS project was performed first using the “Importance-Urgency” matrix. Topics 5, 9 and 15 were identified as top priority topics due to their high importance (see Figure 7).

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Figure 7: Importance Vs Urgency matrix

Next, the rest of the topics were analysed using the Impact-Effort matrix (see Figure 8). Topics 7, 10, 11 and 19 were identified as other top priority topics due to their high impact.

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

Figure 8: Impact vs Effort matrix

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

5 Top prioritized topics

At the end, it was agreed to join some of the selected top priority topics to arrive to the set end goal of 3 final priority topics. These topics, together with their main challenges and needs are outlined in Table 11.

Priority	Topics	Description of the topic	Main challenges	Main needs
1	9+15	Identification of regulatory discrepancies for free release, unconditional and conditional clearance. Analysis of criteria and guidance for clearance and for reuse and recycling	Different national regulations	Promote harmonised criteria and regulations (policies) to enable re-use and recycling, preserve natural resources and minimising the waste to be disposed of
2	5+7	Benchmarking of approaches implemented in nuclear fields for reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site) Benchmarking of available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field	Different approaches/regulations (eg. for non-nuclear into nuclear)	Sharing of best practices and gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning and for minimising waste and recovering and reusing valuable materials
3	10+11+19	Socio-economical assessment of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular) including analysis of costs and time needed for implementation of recycling solutions and identification of societal constraints and ways to overcome these constraints	Societal and Economical	Assess the economical, environmental/societal benefits and facilitate decision making Promote use and create market for recycled materials

Table 11: Top Prioritised Topics

Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)

The Prioritisation process together with the top Prioritised Topics was presented during the Joint Stakeholder webinar held on 30th May 2023 to communicate outcomes of Stakeholder engagement process.